

Zootopia - Verbal Adaptation 4

Judy Hopps is a police officer. She wants to help people, but she is just in charge of the parking tickets. She hates it.

Someone is yelling: "Out of my way, fox!" Someone is yelling at a fox. And that fox looks suspicious to Judy. Very suspicious.

Judy watches him. The fox enters an elephant ice cream shop. This makes Judy more curious. She watches him from outside the shop, through the glass of the front door.

Inside, there is a problem. The elephant shopkeeper is yelling: "We do not want you here, fox. Out!"

Judy enters the ice cream shop.

The fox says to the elephant shopkeeper: "I do not want to disturb, sir. I just want a popsicle..."

Judy gets ready to stop the fox. But then, the fox points to a little boy standing next to him. "...a popsicle for my son."

Judy gets surprised. The fox shows a friendly smile and continues speaking with the elephant shopkeeper: "He loves elephant's things. He wants to be an elephant." Judy looks at the boy: he is a small, cheerful fox and he is wearing a cute little elephant costume. Judy lets out a tender sigh: "Aww..."

But the elephant is still angry. He says: "Listen to me, pal. We do not want foxes here. So, get out!"

Judy decides to step in: "Mmm... Excuse me. I want to buy a popsicle," she says, showing her police badge to the elephant.

The elephant sighs and looks at her. "OK, officer. Which one?"

Judy has no idea, so she whispers to the boy, "Which one I want?"

The little boy points excitedly to a big, red popsicle.

The elephant gives them the popsicle, and they leave the shop. "Thank you so much, Officer Hopps," says the fox. Judy smiles back and says: "Do not worry about it."

Judy asks to the boy: "So, you want to be an elephant, little guy?" The boy nods. Judy smiles warmly. "You can be whatever you want."

Father and son walk away while they wave, "Bye and thanks, Officer Hopps!"

Judy returns to work, but happier.

After a while, she sees the boy again. She calls him happily: "Hey, little elephant! How are y...?"

But she stops. "What... the... hell...?"

She sees the fox melting the popsicle. The boy helps him. The fox takes jars with the melting popsicle into a van. And he drives away.

Actually, the boy drives away.

Judy sees in shock the van going away. She yells: "WHAT THE HELL?!"

To be continued.